

SCIENTIFIC AND METHODOLOGICAL DEVELOPING
PROFESSIONAL COMPETENCES TECHNOLOGICAL EDUCATION
TEACHERS IN HIGH EDUCATION

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Annotatsiya maqolada “Texnologik ta’lim” yo‘nalishidagi talabalarni Bugungi kundagi ta’lim tizimida olib borilayotgan islohotlar talabalarni individual ta’lim traektoriyalariga asoslangan mustaqil fikrlashini rivojlantirish, talabalarda kreativ fikrlash, amaliy ko‘nikmalarni shakllantirishga oid muammolarni bartaraf etishga qaratilgandir. Mustaqil ta’lim olish etuk mutaxassis bo‘lib etishishning muhim omili hisoblanadi.

Kalit so‘zlar: Kasbiy kompetensiya, texnologiya, mustaqil ta’lim, bilim, ko‘nikma, malaka, kompetent, texnologik jarayon, texnik ob’ekt.

Аннотация В статье обучение студентов по направлению “Технологическое образование”, проводимое в современной системе образования, ориентировано на развитие самостоятельного мышления учащегося, адаптированного к индивидуальному учебному процессу, активного мышления у учащегося, формирование Самостоятельное образование является важным фактором становления зрелого ученика.

Ключевые слова: Профессиональная компетентность, технология, самостоятельное образование, знания, умения, компетентность, компетентность, технологический японский, технический объект.

Annotation in the article “Technological education” students in the direction of “Technological education”. Today's reforms in the education system are aimed at developing independent thinking of students based on individual educational trajectories, eliminating problems related to the formation of creative thinking and practical skills in students. Independent education Learning is an important factor in becoming a mature professional.

Key words: Professional competence, technology, independent education, knowledge, skill, qualification, competent, technological process, technical object.

The main share of the development of university education at the world level is the independent work of students, and the main focus is clearly observed in the trend of transition from teaching to learning. In this regard, it became clear that with the transition to a competency-based approach in education, it is necessary to form a system of skills and qualifications for independent work, and to educate the culture of independent work in students. “Strategic goals and priorities of the development of the higher education system” of the Concept of the Development of the Higher Education System of the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030 “Expanding the coverage of higher education, improving the quality of training of highly educated specialists” “Independent increasing the share of educational hours, students’ independent education, critical and creative thinking, systematic analysis, formation of entrepreneurial skills, introduction of methods and technologies aimed at strengthening competencies in the educational process, practical skills in the educational process formation, in this regard, the wide introduction of advanced pedagogical technologies, educational programs and educational materials based on international educational standards into the educational process” and independent education of learners , special attention is paid to the development of the necessary competencies of specialists, creative creativity, research, and logical thinking through continuous improvement of independent work skills. The reforms carried out in the education system today are aimed at developing students' independent thinking based on individual educational trajectories, eliminating problems related to the formation of creative thinking and practical skills in students. A step-by-step transition to the implementation of these tasks is planned in higher education institutions. In the modern educational process, in addition to independent work in the audience, development of analytical abilities, control and planning of study time, development of skills and competencies of rational organization of educational work, independent search for necessary information, creative creation of educational material in the audience perception and It is considered as a form of educational organization capable of providing understanding, various forms of students' knowledge activities in the audience.

Therefore, independent work is a form of organizing the educational process and stimulates students' activity, independence and interest in learning. Independent education is an important factor in becoming a mature specialist. This is especially evident in the vocational training system. Our ancestors also attached importance to the young generation's acquisition of a profession, becoming a mature, well-educated person serving development. The great scholars of the East emphasized the importance of hard work and the acquisition of a profession in their

works. Great thinkers such as Muhammad al - Khorazmi, Abu Ali ibn Sina, Al-Farghani, Ahmad Yassavi, Yusuf Khos-Hajib, Sheikh Najmuddin Kubra, Bahovuddin Naqshbandi, Abdurrahman Jami, Imam al-Bukhari, Ahmad Yugnaki and Alisher Nawai, used hard work, their those who glorified unceasing research and profession

The above - mentioned great scholars in their lives and creative activities have emphasized the importance of independent research in the pursuit of a profession, as well as glorifying the acquisition of a profession. Organization of independent education as a pedagogical problem has been studied by several scientists in their works. Positive features of independent work and independent education, from scientists: V.I. Andpianova's teaching of independent work in the Russian language class in the 5 - 6th grades of Uzbek schools, O.B. Berdieva's formation of independent work skills and competencies in geometry education methodology of E.I.Zakinov's pedagogical basis of organizing independent work in grades 6 - 8, ON.Cultonova's methodology of organizing independent educational activities of students in physics, professional knowledge and skills of young people in the vocational education system of O'.Q.Tolipov and pedagogical technologies of skill development, Sh.Sharipovs pedagogical foundations of forming inventive creativity in students, N.A. Muslimov and O.A. Koysinovs theory and methodology of organizing independent education in the training of vocational teachers, Sh. Yunusova's formation of students' independent educational activities, Z. Nishonova, J. Tolipova and N. Khalilov's research on independent education forms was considered. Considering the idea of developing students' mental powers, he noted: "Development and education cannot be given and delivered to any person. Everyone should achieve this by personal activity." What a person does not own independently is not considered his own, he said. After studying a number of scientific and pedagogical research works, he concluded that "Independent education is a form of education in the higher education system in which educational activities are managed by a pedagogue, assignments are given, advice is organized, and implementation is monitored." emphasizes .

In particular, in some of the works in this regard, it is noticeable that the organization of students' independent education is approached from a personal point of view. Independent education is considered as an important factor in the formation of a person who is active, who strives to achieve high results in improving his professional skills in education, and who comes from the needs of society in choosing and acquiring the pedagogic profession. Taking into account that independent education is controlled by the person himself,

with this activity, a person can freely and at any time choose the resources and use them from the point of view of purpose, means, and content. Autonomy in independent learning is the ability to determine and choose educational goals, principles, content, methods and tools, to implement them without difficulty and without the help of external influences. Since independent education is directly related to independent thinking, it is appropriate to mention the definition given to it: "Independent thinking is a person's knowledge and life experiences, defining the goals and objectives of the person before him. , is a mental activity that consists of solving independently at the level of one's intellectual capabilities, using different ways, methods, and tools." The content of the independent work of the students by the teacher, the active organization of independent work, the fulfillment of the didactic goals set before them and the time specially allocated for it is understood. It is necessary to form the interest and ability to acquire independent knowledge in the future teachers who are studying in the field of technological education as a factor that encourages the improvement of pedagogical culture.

Pedagogical improvement, deepening of professional knowledge and improvement of skills are required from future teachers who are studying in the direction of technological education as an important factor in solving the problem. Students determine the goals and tasks that make up the content of independent education, depending on the strength and motivational reasons that arouse interest in independent education. This can be expressed as follows:

1. Political independent education, modern reality and attitude towards them, which are considered important in conducting independent activities;
2. Professional independent education in the preparatory period aimed at carrying out activities in the chosen direction, mastering the student's independent education;
3. Independent education focused on deeper learning of academic subjects, personal life plans, personal interest;
4. Independent education related to the development of one's talents and hobbies.
5. Independent education aimed at developing one's own character. Professional independent education is the main factor in the development of a person and serves as a description of his ability to work independently in his future activities. The content of independent education depends on the ability to find opportunities for independent education, not directly affecting the nature of work, but indirectly. The future teacher should direct the activities of independent

improvement of his knowledge to a specific goal and to achieve this goal, he must comply with the following conditions.

1. The content of the independent improvement of one's knowledge should be adapted to the specific conditions in the training workshop of the educational institution where the pedagogical practice in the future technological education specialty is taking place, the conditions and requirements of the practice.

2. The future teacher should develop the following qualities based on a certain goal and in a certain order:

- to deeply feel and understand the aspirations and interests of students, to be able to take into account their spiritual needs;

- establishing an emotional connection with students, actively influencing aspects of their intellectual, moral and practical activities.

3. The future teacher must independently study the list of questions on general pedagogy, psychology, occupational hygiene and physiology, technical and technological sciences.

4. The future teacher should choose the most effective methods and ways of the work system to improve his pedagogical skills, choose the right technological process and technical objects.

5. Taking into account specific conditions and in accordance with them, it is desirable for the future teacher to use the forms of improving his knowledge individually or together with the team, to perform practical exercises.

We have considered the opinions and definitions of the above-mentioned research scientists about the processes of organizing independent education and the tasks, goals and conditions of future teachers in this regard. We will consider the scientific-methodological importance of independent education in the development of professional competences of future teachers on the example of the “Technological education” direction, “Technical creativity and construction science”. The purpose of forming the special competence of the future teacher of technological education in “Technical creativity and construction science learning” is to create a fully mastered qualified teacher along with a number of tasks to be performed in technological education. is to create conditions for the formation of a specialist and competent high-tech teacher. Taking into account that the main hour of this subject is made up of practical training courses, a lot of time is needed for the student to complete practical training assignments. Naturally, in order to become a mature specialist in his field, a student must constantly search for himself and be able to independently perform design processes. For this, the student should either improve his professional skills in extracurricular processes, or improve his

knowledge by studying. In this regard, it is important to develop the professional competencies of future technology teachers who are studying in the direction of “Technological education” in higher educational institutions. The in-depth knowledge acquired by the technology teacher during classes and group work is of great importance in independent work, practical application, creation of new projects, and research. The role of independent education is incomparable in the formation of future teachers as mature specialists and success in the field of their future work.

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